

Holocene Climate and the Caspian Sea
A Coupled Climate, Hydrological and Sea Level Model Approach

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Cover photograph shows a man-made construction affected by oscillating Caspian Sea level,
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Foreword

This paper was completed as a research project for the Palaeoclimate and Geo-Ecosystems MSc course at the Faculty of Earth and Life Sciences (FALW), of the Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam. Due to the interdisciplinary nature of this research, the Institute for Environmental Studies (IVM) and Delft Hydraulics (WL Delft) were also involved in both setting out the goals of the research as well as providing the resources needed for carrying it out. FALW, IVM and WL Delft were represented by Hans Renssen, Jeroen Aerts and Jaap Kwadijk, respectively. I would like to thank all three for their input and guidance.

Previous to this research I had very little experience with GIS and hydrological modelling. In this respect, I would like to thank PhD students Hans de Moel and Philip Ward for kindly taking time out to provide me with help and advice on these matters.

Table of Contents

<u>1.0 Introduction</u>	7
1.1 Research Goals	8
<u>2.0 Analysis of the Caspian Sea Water Balance</u>	9
2.1 Brief Introduction to the Caspian Sea	9
2.2 Caspian Sea Level Water Balance	10
2.2.1 Runoff	11
2.2.2 Evaporation	13
2.2.3 Precipitation	13
2.2.4 Flow to the Bay of Koraz-Bogaz-Gol	14
2.3 Climate Processes Affecting the Caspian Water Balance	14
2.4 Twentieth Century Caspian Sea Level Changes	15
2.5 Historical Caspian Sea Level Changes (0 - 1000 BP)	16
2.6 Holocene Caspian Sea Level Changes	17
2.7 Future Caspian Sea Level Changes	18
2.8 Long-term Palaeoclimatological Models of Caspian Sea Level	21
<u>3.0 Model Description</u>	22
3.1 Brief Introduction	22
3.2 ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE Model Description	24
3.2.1 ECBILT-CLIO-VECODE Forcings	24
3.2.2 ECBILT-CLIO-VECODE and Natural Variability	25
3.2.3 ECBILT-CLIO-VECODE Limitations	26
3.3 STREAM Model Description	28
3.3.1 STREAM Input Data	29
3.4 Caspian Sea Level Model	29
3.4.1 Analysing Sea Area Change (A_L)	29
3.4.2 Calculating the Caspian Sea Level	31
<u>4.0 Calibration</u>	32
4.1 Calibrating STREAM	32
4.2 Calibrating Over Sea Precipitation and Evaporation Data	35
<u>5.0 Selection and Preparation of Model Runs</u>	39
5.1 20th Century Model Run	39
5.2 6200-5801 BP Model Run	39
5.3 3400-3001 BP Model Run	40
<u>6.0 Results & Discussion</u>	43
6.1 20th Century	43
6.2 6200-5801 BP	46
6.3 3400-3001 BP	48
6.4 Discussion of all Time Slices	49
6.5 Critical Discussion	51
<u>7.0 Conclusion</u>	53
<u>8.0 Future Research</u>	54
<u>Bibliography</u>	55
<u>Appendices</u>	60

List of Figures

Figure 1: Satellite image of the Caspian Sea during 2005 summer.

Figure 2: Correlation between Volga runoff and CSL (Overeem et al., 2003)

Figures 3a and 3b: Volga discharge as measured at Volgograd Gauging station for 1901-1935 (before hydroelectric schemes) and 1961-1984 (after hydroelectric schemes) Data from Vörösmarty et al., 2004.

Figure 4: Caspian Sea river catchments on a 0.5 by 0.5 degree grid. (Renssen and Knoop, 2000)

Figure 5: Approximate Volga catchment location (blue) superimposed on generalised Dec. Jan. Feb. (DJF) atmospheric Sea Level pressure pattern. (Pressure image from Hurrell et al., 2003)

Figure 6: Simplified representation of atmospheric circulation during positive NAO phase. (Figure from Rodionov, 1994)

Figure 7: Observed CSL, 1900-2000 (Hoogendorn 2005, originally from Klige and Myagkov 1992) with superimposed Winter (Dec. Jan. Feb. Mar.) North Atlantic Oscillation Index five year mean in red. (data from Jones et al., 2000)

Figure 8: Observed and Reconstructed CSL, 1900-1992 (Rodionov 1994)

Figure 9: Caspian Sea Level Curve based on Historical Records (Rodionov, 1994).

Figure 10: Caspian Palaeogeography Sea Level Curve (Rychagov, 1997) with the periods modelled in this study superimposed in grey.

Figure 11: IPCC climate model predictions for global mean temperature (IPCC, 2001)

Figure 12: Elguindi and Giorgi's (2006) annual simulated CSL based on 20th century interpolated AOGCM data.

Figures 13a and 13b: Elguindi and Giorgi's (2006) simulated CSL based on 20th and 21st century interpolated AOGCM data in the case of IPCC scenario A2 (top) and IPCC scenario A1b (bottom)

Figure 14: Schematic view of the coupled offline modelling process.

Figure 15a and 15b: June Insolation (top) and GHG (bottom) forcings at 60°N, as used in the ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE model, (Renssen et al., 2005) with the time slices from this study highlighted in grey.

Figure 16: Flowchart of STREAM Modelling Processes (Aerts et al., 1999)

Figure 17: Taking sea area and morphology into account.

Figure 18: Relationship between CSL and sea area.

Figure 19: Calculating the CSL for a given time period.

Figure 20: Modelled (1903-1935) and observed (1903-1935 [Vörösmarty et al, 1998]) Volga monthly mean discharge at Volgograd.

Figure 21: Modelled (1901-2000) and observed (1915-1984 [Vorosmarty et al, 1998]) Ural monthly mean discharge.

Figure 22: Top: Estimated annual Caspian Sea evaporation data for the period 1890-1990 (Rodionov, 1994), with five year running mean. Bottom: ECBilt annual mean over-sea Mediterranean evaporation data for the 20th century, calibrated using mean and standard deviation of Rodionov (1994) Caspian Sea evaporation data, with five year running mean.

Figure 23: Top: Estimated annual mean Caspian Sea precipitation data for the period 1890-1990 (Rodionov, 1994), with five year running mean. Bottom: ECBilt annual mean over-sea Mediterranean precipitation data for the 20th century, calibrated using mean and standard deviation of Rodionov (1994) Caspian Sea precipitation data, with five year running mean.

Figure 24: Calibrated over sea P-E (nine year smooth), modelled STREAM Volga discharge (nine year smooth) and modelled CSL (annual).

Figure 25: Calibrated over sea P-E (nine year smooth), modelled STREAM Volga discharge (nine year smooth) and modelled CSL (yearly).

Figure 26: Calibrated ECBilt over sea P-E (nine year smooth), modelled STREAM Volga discharge (nine year smooth) and modelled CSL (yearly).

Figure 27: Kutzbach and Street-Perrot's (1985) Holocene climate forcings reconstruction.

Figure 28: Uncorrected monthly Mediterranean Evaporation data for three time slices, as simulated by ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE.

List of Tables

Table 1: Caspian Sea Water Budget 1900-1985 (Kobori and Glantz, 1998, adapted from Kosarev and Makarova, 1988)

Table 2: River Runoff Share per River (Shiklomanov et al., 1995)

Table 3: 1901-2000 AD correlation between annual Δ CSL and various factors.

Table 4: 6200-5801 BP correlation between annual Δ CSL and various factors.

Table 5: Average simulated river discharges, average corrected over-sea data and simulated CSL for the 20th century, 6200-5801 BP and 3400-3000 BP.

Table 6: 3400-3000 BP correlation between annual Δ CSL and various factors.

Table 7: Comparison of Caspian Sea Level studies. (ECBilt-STREAM [This study]; Rychagov, 1997; , Rodionov, 1994; Giorgi and Elguindi, 2006)

1.0 Introduction

The Caspian Sea is the largest landlocked body of water in the world. Due to it being a closed system independent of global oceans, the Caspian Sea Level (CSL) is highly sensitive to climate fluctuations and environmental conditions. The main input into the Caspian Sea is river runoff and precipitation over the sea itself and the only loss of water is evaporation from the sea. Changes in these factors will therefore directly influence the CSL.

Scientists and water experts in the 1970s predicted that the sea level would continue to fall and even recommended measures to divert water to the sea in order to maintain a minimum CSL (Rodionov, 1994). National governments assumed that the CSL would rise no further and planned accordingly. However, the experts were proven to be incorrect and the CSL proceeded to rise some 2.5 m during the 1980s and 1990s (Rodionov, 1994). This unexpected rise had caused many coastal facilities and settlements, which were newly built in the expectation of no CSL rise, to be flooded beyond use. It is therefore of the utmost importance to gain more understanding into the CSL fluctuations, especially over longer time periods, so that future predictions can be more accurate, and therefore useful for government planning.

Previous studies have focused on geological reconstructions of past CSL (Rychagov, 1997; Overeem et al., 2003) or modelling of current and future CSL (Elguindi and Giorgi 2005, 2006). There is a lack of palaeomodel reconstructions of the CSL, and the aim of the paper is to address this by modelling CSL throughout the Holocene.

1.1 Research Goals

J. Kwadijk and H. Renssen tabled the idea of using a STREAM model of the Caspian basin, combined with the ECBilt climate model, to simulate the Holocene changes in Caspian Sea level (CSL).

This research project follows on from the work done by De Moel (2005) and Ward (2005) with respect to modelling palaeo-discharges of global rivers using the STREAM model, especially with relation to the Volga River.

The main goals of this research project are:

- to construct a STREAM model for the Caspian basin.
- to create a model for the Caspian Sea water balance and ultimately the CSL, using STREAM discharge data combined with ECBilt precipitation and evaporation data.
- to use this model to investigate the CSL for other time slices, specifically long term, inter-centennial CSL trends and the phenomenon of inter-decadal shifts in sea level.
- to investigate longer term changes in CSL between the Holocene and now.
- to write a scientific paper in the form of a research project, building on previous work by other authors and interpreting findings, as outlined in the research project goals noted in the MSc study guide.

2.0 Analysis of the Caspian Sea Water Balance

Figure 1: Satellite image of the Caspian Sea during 2005 summer¹

100 km

2.1 Brief Introduction to the Caspian Sea

The Caspian Sea is the world's largest lake (371,000 km² [European Space Agency, 2005]) and has no outflow point (see Figure 1). Current sea level is -28 metres elevation (ESA, 2005). Most water input comes from the Volga and Ural rivers in the North. The relatively low-lying Bay of Kara-Bogaz-Gol in the east is connected to the Caspian Sea through a narrow channel through a sandbank, and has evaporation rates higher than the Caspian Sea proper. To the east of the Caspian Sea is an arid, desert area that produces negligible runoff.

¹ NASA, MODIS Rapid Response System Gallery <<http://rapidfire.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov/gallery/?2005162-0611/CaspianSea.A2005162.1010.1km.jpg>>

2.2 Caspian Sea Level Water Balance

In order to understand the basics regarding the fluctuations in CSL, we must first consider the water balance involved. The Caspian Sea can be viewed as a closed lake system with no outflow point, and as such, the basic water balance can be viewed as follows (adapted from Kislov and Surkova, 1998):

$$(P-E)A_L = RA_C \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

P = Precipitation over the sea

E = Evaporation from the sea

A_L = lake area

R = River runoff

A_C = catchment area

When studying timescales short enough that tectonic processes are not of influence, one can assume that the area of the catchment (A_C) will remain constant. In this case, the three main causes of CSL change are changes in Q , A_L and P-E. Therefore, when investigating the relationship between climate and CSL change, the changes in these variables, and their cause, must be studied closely. The averaged annual water budget from 1900 to 1985 was as follows (Table 1):

Component	Loss/Gain (km ³ /year)
River discharge	+298
Sea surface precipitation (P)	+74
Sea surface evaporation (E)	-370
Loss to Bay of Kara-Bogaz-Gol	-14
<i>Total:</i>	-12

Table 1: Caspian Sea Water Budget 1900-1985 (Kobori and Glantz, 1998, adapted from Kosarev and Makarova, 1988)

As the Caspian Sea has no outflow point, evaporation is the only escape for water. Any increase or decrease in runoff or over-sea P-E will therefore directly affect the CSL. Indeed, the CSL is known to vary by as much as 30 cm in one year (Rodionov, 1994). 70% of this variation is estimated to be due to changes in runoff, with 20% due to changes in evaporation on the sea and 8% due to changes in precipitation (Archipova et al., 1970). 2% can be accounted to factors such as thermal expansion, ground water flow and losses to the Bay of Kara-Bogaz-Gol. The bay of Kara-Bogaz-Gol is connected to the Caspian Sea, but through a shallow channel of only 250 metres wide, meaning that it has its own separate hydrological system.

As the CSL rises and falls, so too does the area of the Caspian Sea itself change, according to the morphology of the basin. As the CSL rises, the area of the Caspian Sea increases. This means that the surface area increases, causing more water to be lost through evaporation through exchange with the atmosphere. As well as this, river discharges will have less effect on the CSL, due to being spread over a greater area. For example, if 300 km³ of water is added to a surface area of 300,000 km², it will cause a sea level increase of 1 metre. The same 300 km³ added to a 400,000 km² surface area will cause a sea level increase of just 0.75 m. For reference, the current area of the Caspian Sea is 371,000 km² (European Space Agency, 2005). If river discharge increases or decreases suddenly, the CSL will rise or fall in a dramatic fashion before finding a new equilibrium surface area allowing P, E and R to balance again. In this way the Caspian Sea can be seen as a closed hydrological system that jumps suddenly from one steady state to another when water budget changes are made. Indeed, this can be seen in the sea level curves which will be discussed later in this paper. When taking sea surface area into account, the formula for change in CSL can be expressed as follows (adapted from Rodionov, 1994):

$$\Delta L = Q/A_L + P - E - KBG/A_L \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

Where ΔL is change in CSL in metres, Q is river discharge in m³, KBG is flow to the bay of Kara-Bogaz-Gol in m³, A_L is Caspian Sea surface area in m², P is precipitation in metres and E evaporation in metres.

2.2.1 Runoff

River runoff varies seasonally, with the highest runoff in spring, due to snowmelt runoff. This seasonal signal can also be seen in the discharge pattern of the Volga River (see Figure 3), which contributes over four fifths of runoff (see Table 2). The importance of the Volga to the change in CSL is demonstrated best by Overeem et al. (2003), who found a strong correlation (R=0.8) between the observed Volga discharge for the 20th century and Δ CSL (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Correlation between Volga runoff and CSL (Overeem et al., 2003)

From the 1930s onwards, due to hydroelectric schemes and other such anthropogenic influences, the runoff regime of the Volga has been changed drastically. Discharge is now more evenly spread throughout the year (i.e. a higher base flow), with the spring flood less pronounced (See Figures 3a and 3b). Increased use of Volga waters for agricultural use has also meant that the annual total annual mean discharge has been reduced from 8205 m³/sec to 7382 m³/sec, some 10% (See Figures 3a and 3b).

Figures 3a and 3b: Volga discharge as measured at Volgograd Gauging station for 1901-1935 (before hydroelectric schemes) and 1961-1984 (after hydroelectric schemes) Data from Vörösmarty et al., 2004.

Runoff from rivers can be attributed to the following tributaries:

River(s)	Share of River Runoff
Volga	82%
Ural	3%
Sulak, Samur, Kura and Terek (All Western Coast)	11.5%
Iranian Rivers	3.5%
Total	100%

Table 2: River Runoff Share per River (Shiklomanov et al., 1995)

As can be seen in Table 2, the Volga River is responsible for by far the largest share of river discharge into the Caspian Sea. The Volga River catchment is also by far the largest and reaches west and north to Moscow and beyond, meaning that it is influenced by climate regimes far from the Caspian Sea itself (see Figure 4). To give some idea of scale, the Volga catchment spans from 32°E to 59°E and from 46°N to 62°N. The eastern coast, while being part of the catchment area, receives very little precipitation and has high evaporation rates, making a negligible contribution to Caspian Sea waters.

Figure 4: Caspian Sea river catchments on a 0.5 by 0.5 degree grid. (Renssen and Knoop, 2000)

For model calibration purposes, downstream gauging station data is available on the Volga, with an upstream gauging station also present on the Ural River.

2.2.2 Evaporation

Evaporation over the sea is seasonal and is out of phase with solar insolation due to the buffer effect caused by the heat capacity of the sea, with the highest evaporation taking place in late summer (July-September), two months after maximum insolation. In this respect the Caspian Sea behaves in a similar way to open ocean. Available evaporation data for the Caspian Sea is of low accuracy and is only useful for making general estimates (Rodionov, 1994). The estimate for the 20th century is 97 cm/yr (Rodionov, 1994)

2.2.3 Precipitation

Precipitation over the Caspian Sea is estimated to be 18 cm/yr (Baidin and Kosarev, 1986). Historic observed precipitation data for various weather stations around the Caspian Sea coast (Astrakhan, Baku, Cheleken, Krasnovodsk [WorldClimate, 2006]) were compared for this project and confirmed this as a good estimate.

The Kosarev and Makarova (1988) figure of 74 km³ for 1900-1985, as seen in Table 1, would translate to 19.3 cm/yr precipitation, if we assume the average sea area for the 1900-1985 period was 384,000 km² (corresponding approximately to a CSL of -27 m elevation). In this respect the Kosarev and Makarova (1988) estimate differs somewhat from that of Baidin and Kosarev (1986).

2.2.4 Flow to the Bay of Koraz-Bogaz-Gol

Overspill to the Bay of Koraz-Bogaz-Gol averages 10 km³ annually (Rodionov 1994) and is dependent on CSL. Higher CSL will result in more overspill into the bay, and lower CSL leads to less overspill.

2.3 Climate Processes Affecting the Caspian Water Balance

Processes such as North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) play an important role in controlling the amount of precipitation over the Volga catchment and there is a strong linkage between CSL changes and NAO (Rodionov, 1994). The North Atlantic Oscillation index is defined as the difference in surface air pressure between the Icelandic low (IL) and Azores high (AH). During a positive NAO index phase, the Icelandic low grows more influential over the Volga catchment, bringing more moisture and precipitation to the area, due to stronger westerlies from the Atlantic Ocean. Precipitation over much of the Volga catchment falls as snow during the winter months, building up during this cold period. This extra snow will in turn cause increased runoff when the spring melt occurs. A positive winter NAO will therefore cause more snow build-up. According to Popova (2005), the CSL rise seen since the 1970s has been due to increased snow depth in winter caused by positive NAO.

During a negative NAO phase, the Icelandic low weakens, meaning that the Siberian high (S_H) is allowed to exert more influence over the Volga catchment, leading to drier conditions. See Figure 5 for the location of the Volga catchment in relation to the Icelandic low and Siberian high.

Figure 5: Approximate Volga catchment location (blue) superimposed on generalised Dec. Jan. Feb. (DJF) atmospheric Sea Level pressure pattern. (Pressure image from Hurrell et al., 2003) I_L stands for Icelandic Low, A_H for Azores High and S_H for Siberian High. Blue arrow indicates prevailing wind direction.

NAO circulation can also influence the temperature in the Caspian Sea area. A positive NAO phase will increase the circulation of cold air towards the Caspian Sea, therefore reducing over-sea evaporation. See Figure 6.

Figure 6: Simplified representation of atmospheric circulation during positive NAO phase. (Figure from Rodionov, 1994)

A positive NAO phase will therefore cause the double effect of both increased precipitation over the Volga catchment as well as reduced evaporation over the Caspian Sea. This means that NAO is extremely influential upon changes in CSL.

2.4 Twentieth Century Caspian Sea Level Changes

Due to the sensitivity of the Caspian Sea to changes in precipitation, river discharge and evaporation, the CSL has seen numerous dramatic changes in height throughout the past century and throughout the Holocene as a whole.

Figure 7: Observed CSL, 1900-2000 (Hoogendorn 2005, originally from Klige and Myagkov 1992) with superimposed Winter (Dec. Jan. Feb. Mar.) North Atlantic Oscillation Index five year mean in red. (data from Jones et al., 2000)

Twentieth century, instrumentally observed fluctuations in CSL are detailed in Figure 7. Originally it was thought that anthropogenic influences, such as river damming, diversion, large scale modern industrial agriculture and the resultant reduction in river runoff were the sole cause of the reduction in CSL witnessed between 1930 and 1975. The sudden rise in CSL, between 1975 and 1995, came therefore as a great surprise to many. As can be seen in Figure 7, there seems to be a strong relationship between CSL and NAO, for the reasons explained in earlier Section 2.2.

Figure 8: Observed and Reconstructed CSL, 1900-1992 (Rodionov 1994)

In Figure 8 we can see a comparison between the observed CSL and the reconstructed CSL (Rodionov 1994). Rodionov's "reconstructed CSL" represents what the CSL would be like without anthropogenic interruptions to river discharge, e.g. hydroelectric schemes. Up until about 1940 the reconstructed and observed trends seem to go hand in hand, after which they diverge. It is worth noting that the first dam on the Volga was built in 1937, with subsequent dams completed throughout the rest of the twentieth century. As can be seen, human influence during this period causes the CSL to be lower in general, although the same inherent variability is still present in both scenarios.

One could therefore conclude that natural variability and human influence over the runoff are independent factors which both influence the CSL. While anthropogenic interference plays a large role in reducing the amount of river runoff reaching the Caspian Sea and therefore the CSL as a whole, it does not seem to suppress the inherent annual and decadal variability in the runoff itself.

2.5 Historical Caspian Sea Level Changes (0 - 1000 BP)

Historical records for CSL change are sparse and sometimes conflicting. Rodionov (1994) collected various historical information to try and approximate a sea level curve (Figure 9). According to these historical accounts, the CSL was very low during the 11th to 13th centuries. Evidence includes the existence of harbours and city walls which could only exist in the case of a low CSL. River deltas were also examined. CSL Estimates for this

era vary from -29 m to -31.7 m. This period coincides with the Medieval Warm Period, a time of mild winters and drier summers in Europe (Moberg et al., 2005).

Figure 9: Caspian Sea Level Curve based on Historical Records (Rodionov, 1994).

The consensus regarding the CSL in the fourteenth century is that it rose sharply. However, there is disagreement regarding the magnitude of the rise. Rodionov refers to palaeogeographic studies by Varushchenko et al. (1987), showing that the CSL of the 14th and 15th centuries couldn't be higher than -26 m. Historical records gathered by Rodionov show that the CSL dropped in the 16th century, possibly as low as -29 m, however Rodionov does not include this much of a drop in his graphical reconstruction (Figure 9). The distance measured between the coast and the city of Astrakahn by an English traveller named Jenkinson in 1558 is used to estimate the Caspian Sea area, giving the CSL estimate of -29 (Gumilyov 1980).

In the 17th century, the CSL was found to rise. Berg (1934) details accounts of water rising to reach city walls that were, some 34 years earlier, surrounded by a half-mile dry land. The CSL remained relatively high in the 17th – 19th century, but strong inter-decadal fluctuations (as much as 12 cm/yr) were noted (Rodionov, 1994).

2.6 Holocene Caspian Sea Level Changes

Rychagov (1997) studied the delta formation of small rivers draining into the Caspian Sea. These have steep gradients, lower sediment transport and no fan deltas, meaning that, according to Rychagov, they are better suited for recording changes in the CSL. There are some doubts however as to how accurate the Carbon-14 dating of the marine shells used in this reconstruction is (H.B. Vonhof, personal communication). See Figure 10 for Rychagov's CSL curve.

Figure 10: Caspian Palaeogeography Sea Level Curve (Rychagov, 1997) with the periods modelled in this study superimposed in grey.

Analysis of the Kura river delta by Hoogendoorn et al. (2005), while producing no CSL curve, found transgressions and regressions which agree with the CSL curve of Rychagov (1997).

2.7 Future Caspian Sea Level Changes

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC] (2001), global temperature is set to rise in the 21st century, the amount by which is dependent on the CO₂ emissions scenario and model being employed (see Figure 11). However, all scenarios agree with each other in the sense that they predict considerable global climate warming.

Figure 11: IPCC climate model predictions for global mean temperature (IPCC, 2001)

Elguindi and Giorgi (2006) used climate data from the Atmosphere-Ocean General Circulation Models (AOGCM), as used in the IPCC predictions for

CO₂ emissions scenario A2 (ca. 850 ppm CO₂ by 2100) and A1b (ca. 700 ppm CO₂ by 2100) to model Caspian Sea level changes in the 21st century. Crucially, they only selected AOGCMs with a resolution high enough so that the Caspian Sea would be included in the grid raster. The AOGCMs selected include volcanic and solar forcing for the 20th century. AOGCM data over the Caspian basin area is interpolated to a 50 by 50 kilometre resolution. Giorgi and Elguindi don't use a hydrological model to simulate river discharge, but instead use an equation that they have devised to take precipitation, evaporation and sea area into account:

$$\Delta CSL = \left[\frac{A_L}{A_S} [P_L(1 - fl) - E_L] + P_S - D - E_S \right] \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

CSL = sea level increment
A_L = land area, A_S = sea area
P_L = precipitation over land, P_S = precipitation over sea
E_L = evaporation over land, E_S = evaporation over sea
D = discharge to bay of Kara-Bogaz-Gol
fl = percentage of runoff loss

This equation was shown to be acceptably accurate in a previous study undertaken (Elguindi and Giorgi, 2005), whereby a regional model was used for the Caspian basin area.

Since Elguindi and Giorgi (2006) don't use a hydrological model, they use the variable *fl* to represent all losses in runoff not due to soil evaporation. A different *fl* value is employed depending on the AOGCM being used, which seems to be used as a form of calibration, depending on the model. In the case of using a hydrological model, this would be achieved by calibrating river basins according to observed gauging data. The equation model was run with the interpolated data from seven AOGCM models, for both the 20th and 21st century.

Figure 12: Elguindi and Giorgi's (2006) annual simulated CSL based on 20th century interpolated AOGCM data.

As can be seen in Fig. 12, the ensemble average stays within the range of the observed sea level variations for the 20th century. The separate climate models show sudden decadal, variations, but none accurately recreate the observed CSL for the 20th century.

Figures 13a and 13b: Elguindi and Giorgi's (2006) simulated CSL based on 20th and 21st century interpolated AOGCM data in the case of IPCC scenario A2 (top) and IPCC scenario A1b (bottom)

Giorgi and Elguindi's ensemble average for the 21st century shows an overall decreasing trend to between -33 and -34 m.in CSL for both the A2 (Fig. 13a) and A1b (Fig. 13b) scenarios (as seen in Fig. 11), despite a disparity of predictions (a range of some 25 metres) by the individual models. The IPCC models Elguindi and Giorgi use model all simulate increased precipitation over the Caspian basin in the 21st century, which agrees with the findings of Aerts et al. (2006), who modelled Volga discharge as increasing under the A2

scenario. Despite this, Elguindi and Giorgi still simulate a decrease in CSL, due to over-sea evaporation increasing by an even larger extent, leading to a net deficit in the water balance.

Needless to say, a sea level decrease to -35 m, possibly unseen in the Holocene, would have negative ecological consequences for the Caspian Sea and would be an economic disaster for the Caspian area.

2.8 Long-term Palaeoclimatological Models of Caspian Sea Level

As was inferred in the introduction section of this paper, there does not seem to be, as yet, any simulations of Caspian Sea Level made on longer, palaeo timescales. With this in mind, it was decided to use the data from ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE model runs for the Holocene to analyse CSL fluctuations for various Holocene time slices, in order to give further insight into pre-industrial Holocene CSL trends.

3.0 Model Description

3.1 Brief Introduction

Before the method used to obtain the results is explained in full detail, a brief overview of the modelling approach used will be given. In this research project, the CSL is simulated through the offline coupling of a climatological model, hydrological model and sea level model.

The climatological model used is the ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE, an Earth System Model of Intermediate Complexity (EMIC), which consists of three coupled models representing atmospheric (ECBilt), sea ice (CLIO) and vegetation (VECODE) components.

The resulting precipitation and temperature data from the climatological model is used as input data for the STREAM hydrological model of the Caspian basin, which simulates river discharge.

River discharge generated by the hydrological model is then used, along with over-sea precipitation and evaporation data from the climatological model, and morphological data of the basin, to simulate CSL.

For a graphical overview of the modelling processes involved, see Figure 14.

Figure 14: Schematic view of the coupled offline modelling process.

3.2 ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE Model Description

ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE is a coupled atmosphere, sea ice and vegetation model. It is an Earth System Model of Intermediate Complexity (EMIC), as described by Claussen et al. (2002). An EMIC model is of simple enough complexity so that it can be run on a standard personal computer.

The atmospheric component is modelled by ECBilt, developed by the Royal Dutch Meteorological Institute (KNMI) (Opsteegh et al., 1998). This model has a reduced complexity when compared to a GCM, which allows it to run satisfactorily on a standard personal computer. The spatial resolution involved is T21, which translates approximately as 5.6° latitude by 5.6° longitude grid.

The CLIO model, developed at the Université Catholique de Louvain, is responsible for modelling of ocean circulation as well as the extent and distribution of sea ice (Goosse & Fichefet, 1999). CLIO is an OGCM using a spatial resolution of 3° by 3° with 20 vertical levels. Interpolation is used to couple the differing spatial resolutions of the CLIO and ECBilt components.

Vegetation is modelled by the VECODE component, developed at the Potsdam Institut für Klimafolgenforschung. This model (Brovkin et al., 2002) simulates vegetation on a global scale, computing the response of grassland, trees and bare soil (desert) to climate change. These results are used to estimate the land albedo effect only, and not for other processes, such as evapotranspiration.

3.2.1 ECBILT-CLIO-VECODE Forcings

The ECBILT-CLIO-VECODE model was used to simulate the transient Holocene climate of the past 9,000 years (Renssen et al., 2005). As such the model was forced using long term forcings, namely orbital parameters and greenhouse gases. Orbital parameters affecting solar insolation reaching earth have been calculated by astro-physicists (Berger, 1978) and greenhouse gases were prescribed according to ice core records (Raynaud et al., 2000) and, for more recent times, with the help of observations (Keeling and Whorf, 2000). See Figure 15 for an overview of the forcings used.

Figure 15a and 15b: June Insolation (top) and GHG (bottom) forcings at 60°N, as used in the ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE model, (Renssen et al., 2005) with the time slices from this study highlighted in grey.

3.2.2 ECBILT-CLIO-VECODE and Natural Variability

In order to model variability in Caspian Sea Level, it is therefore important that the EMIC can model natural variability in the atmosphere-ocean system, especially NAO. Studies have been undertaken to determine if the ECBilt-CLIO-Vecode model reproduces natural variability. According to Selten et al. (1999), “the North Atlantic variability in the ECBilt coupled integration compares qualitatively well with observations and a state-of-the-art GCM, although its climatology is considerably warmer.” The ECBilt run by Selten et al. had no flux correction applied, so this would explain why the climatology was generally warmer.

3.2.3 ECBILT-CLIO-VECODE Limitations

Like any model, the ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE model is a mathematical approximation of reality, and therefore has its limitations. The first and most striking limit from the standpoint of this investigation is that the Caspian Sea is not represented in the ECBilt model. Due to the low resolution, the Caspian Sea is viewed as a land cell void of water.

Secondly, we know that the CSL is vulnerable to sudden short-term decadal shifts in the regional hydrological balance, causing it to shift from steady state to steady state. It is therefore important that the model employed accurately reproduces regional changes in climate. The model has a low resolution and does not model feedbacks associated with cloud cover (Goosse et al., 2005), which both could hinder the model's ability to model regional climate changes.

When considering short-term, decadal shifts in the hydrological balance, it is also important to note that the particular ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE model run used in this research project did not include volcanic forcing or changes in solar output. The model does allow for these to be included, however.

Another weakness in the ECBilt model is the fact that it uses flux correction. Excess precipitation over the North Atlantic is moved to the South Pacific in order to make up for a shortage in precipitation there.

3.3 STREAM Model Description

The STREAM model (available for download at <http://www.geo.vu.nl/users/ivmstream/>), developed by the Institute for Environmental Studies at the Vrije Universiteit in Amsterdam, was used to model the hydrological processes of the Caspian Basin. Using input data for land use, groundwater characteristics, elevation, precipitation and temperature, the model is able to calculate water discharge for each cell (Aerts et al., 1999).

The model was run at a resolution of 0.5 by 0.5 degrees longitude and latitude, and on a monthly timestep. (Palaeo)climate simulations of temperature and precipitation for input into the STREAM model were based on data sets from previous runs of the ECBilt-CLIO-Vecode EMIC run according to the forcings listed in Section 3.2.1.

Figure 16: Flowchart of STREAM Modelling Processes (Aerts et al., 1999)

Initial conditions are set for snow cover, soil saturation, groundwater capacity and accumulated potential water loss. These are set in the form of initial maps (init maps) which set are set at a starting value, in this case zero. These are then recalculated by STREAM for each passing time step. STREAM also internally calculates the snowfall, snowmelt, groundwater movement, evapotranspiration and water flow per grid cell for each time step. For each time step STREAM produces a grid map of the model area for aridity (actual evapotranspiration / potential evapotranspiration), snow cover, discharge, temperature and precipitation (see Figure 16).

3.3.1 STREAM Input Data

The input data was prepared according to the STREAM model manual, which can be downloaded at <http://www.geo.vu.nl/users/ivmstream/>. A brief description of the input data used follows below.

The United States Geological Survey (USGS) GTOPO30 digital elevation model was used to derive a flow direction map in IDRISI for the entire Caspian basin, with the Volga catchment flow map of De Moel (2005) superimposed (see Appendix D). The constraining area was defined using a 0.5 by 0.5 degree Caspian basin derived from the TerrainBase DEM from the National Geophysical Data Centre, coupled with the catchment mask of Renssen and Knoop (2000). The 0.5 by 0.5 degree conversion method was based on the method as described by Renssen and Knoop (2000).

Land cover characteristics (known as crop factor, or cropf) were prescribed to the model from the USGS Global Land Cover Characterisation, Version 1.2. The land cover map is an annual average based on 1992 land cover, reduced to 0.5 by 0.5 degree resolution. The crop factor maps are used to help calculate the influence of vegetation upon STREAM flow, specifically the effect of evapotranspiration.

Temperature and precipitation data from the ECBilt-Clio-Vecode model was prescribed to the STREAM model on a monthly basis. The ECBilt-Clio-Vecode model output data has a resolution of 5.6 by 5.6 degrees, and had to be downscaled to 0.5 by 0.5 degrees before it could be used as input data for the stream model. Some smoothing was applied during the downscaling process. The data was prepared in this way by De Moel (2005) according to the downscaling methods of Bouwer et al. (2004).

A heat map was created for the area being modelled, following the Thornwaite and Mather (1955) equation. The Thornwaite and Mather equation is used to help calculate evapotranspiration. This equation allows for evapotranspiration to be approximated based on temperature data only, when data for other factors such as wind speed is not available. For STREAM to calculate evapotranspiration in this way, a “heat map” was prepared by processing all monthly temperature for each time slice as follows:

$$H = HEAT = \sum_{jan}^{dec} \left(\frac{T_m}{5} \right)^{1.514} \quad (Equation 4)$$

T_m = average monthly temperature.

An “A map” is then calculated on the basis of the heat map, using the following equation:

$$A = 0.49239 + 0.01792 \cdot H - 0.0000771771 \cdot H^2 + 0.000000675 \cdot H^3 \quad (Equation 5)$$

3.4 Caspian Sea Level Model

All STREAM cells discharging into the Caspian Sea were found on the flow direction map (see Appendix D) and marked to be analysed in STREAM. By analysing STREAM runoff into the Caspian Sea, as well as ECBilt-Clio-Vecode data for evaporation and precipitation over the Caspian Sea, the water balance for Caspian Sea can be estimated, as detailed in Section 2.2, Equation 2 ($\Delta L = Q/A_L + P - E - KBG/A_L$).

3.4.1 Analysing Sea Area Change (A_L)

As was discussed earlier (Section 2.2), the dynamic nature of the sea area (A_L) has consequences for the influence of evaporation and runoff on the changing sea level. Rodionov (1994) also mentions that changing evaporation and discharge regimes cause the CSL to reach a new equilibrium level, with a corresponding surface area.

At first a “bathtub” model was used for the Caspian Sea. This was found to be unsuitable because the constant surface area (A_L). The CSL was found to rise indefinitely because the bathtub model could not find a new equilibrium area that balanced evaporation and runoff.

"Bathtub" model

In the bathtub model, a rising sea level has no consequence for the area of the sea, meaning that evaporation and discharge continue to exert the same influence.

Morphological Model

A rise in sea level in the morphological model causes the sea area to increase. This means that losses due to evaporation increase and that river discharge exerts less influence.

Figure 17: Taking sea area and morphology into account.

A morphological model, in the form of a hypsometrical curve, was required to accurately model the area of the Caspian Sea. As such, the morphology of the Caspian area had to be taken into account. For this, the same USGS GTOPO 30 digital elevation model that was used for the flow analysis was analysed in IDRISI. The map was first cropped so that only the Caspian Sea's immediate basin was visible, and then re-projected to a Lambert equal area projection, in such a way that each pixel was equal to 1 km². The number of pixels (km²) for each metre of elevation was then cumulatively counted in IDRISI (see Figure 18).

Figure 18: Relationship between CSL and sea area.

Surprisingly, the relationship between elevation and area was found to be almost perfectly linear ($R^2=0.99$). This means that the equation of the line can be used to accurately estimate the area of the Caspian Sea for any given elevation:

$$A_L = 8305.7 \cdot L + 608239 \quad (\text{Equation 6})$$

A_L = Area of the lake (km²)
 L = CSL (metres elevation)

The current observed elevation and area is -28 m and 371,000 km², respectively (ESA, 2005). Using Equation 6 gives a modelled area of 375,679 km² for -28 m, which is accurate to 98.7%. Only elevations above -28 msl (the current CSL) could be analysed, as the GTOPO30 DEM data does not extend below the current Caspian Sea surface. It is assumed that the same linear function is valid for lower elevations. Fortunately, -28 m is a relatively low elevation as far as Holocene CSL values go, so modelling sea levels below this elevation will probably not be necessary for most time slices.

3.4.2 Calculating the Caspian Sea Level

Using the sea level function Equation 2 (Rodionov, 1994) and the lake area function Equation 6, combined with the data for river discharge, over sea precipitation and evaporation, the change in sea level can be calculated for each iteration as shown in Figure 19.

For the annual loss due to runoff into the Bay of Kara-Bogaz-Gol (KBG/ A_L) a constant value of 2.7 cm/yr was prescribed, corresponding roughly to the 10 km³ yearly value as estimated by Rodionov (1994). According to Elguindi and Giorgi (2006), who use a constant value of 3 cm/yr, this annual loss is very minor and does not effect the CSL calculations much.

Figure 19: Calculating the CSL for a given time period.

ΔL is calculated for each iteration, leading to a new CSL for every iteration. At the start of a model run an initial sea level value has to be manually prescribed. For more recent runs, such as the 20th century, the corresponding observed values can be prescribed as an initial value.

In the case of palaeo time periods, where no observed data is available, a sensitivity experiment with many different starting values must be run, in order to ascertain which equilibrium range the simulated CSL for that time period seeks. This process takes about 150 years, depending on the start value used. A value in the equilibrium range can then be used as the starting value.

4.0 Calibration

STREAM was run with ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE temperature and precipitation input data, and calibrated with the help of discharge data from river gauging stations. As well as this, ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE does not simulate Caspian Sea precipitation and evaporation properly, so this data will also needed to be calibrated.

4.1 Calibrating STREAM

The period 1901-2000 AD was modelled, meaning that 1200 monthly iterations were run in STREAM. The STREAM model was fed with the 1200 corresponding monthly ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE maps for the 20th century, for both temperature and precipitation, smoothed to 0.5° latitude by 0.5° longitude resolution. The GIS Data was prepared as described in Section 3.3.1. This covered the entire Caspian Basin. The gauging station data at Volgograd (Vörösmarty et al., 2004) was used to calibrate the model. The aim at first was to calibrate the 1901-2000 model run with the Volgograd data from 1901-2000. It was decided however that only the observed data from 1901-1935 would be used to calibrate the model, as this was before major anthropogenic changes were brought upon the Volga River. Previous observations were not available. In the end, 1903-1935 was used as the calibration period, because the STREAM values for the first two years (1901 & 1902) are at the beginning of the model run and are highly unrealistic. This is due to the model spin up time required by STREAM. It was not possible to validate the model for another period during the 20th due to the anthropogenic changes brought upon the river regime.

The STREAM cell for Volgograd was analysed and compared to the observed values for 1903-1935. They were found to be very similar, but the discharge in the late summer months (July – September) was found to be overestimated. In order to compensate for this, certain calibration factors were adjusted in STREAM. The factors adjusted control the amount of water that is stored as groundwater, increasing or decreasing the buffer effect groundwater storage has on river discharge. The factors adjusted were the “C” and “TOGW” factors. Raising the TOGW factor causes more water to flow directly into the river and less to be stored as groundwater, thus raising the peak flow and lowering the post-summer lower discharges. The C calibration factor controls the baseflow directly, and its adjustment was also used in the calibration process. After calibration (see Appendix A for script), the following flow regime was modelled for the Volga River at Volgograd (see Figure 20):

Figure 20: Modelled (1903-1935) and observed (1903-1935 [Vörösmarty et al, 1998]) Volga monthly mean discharge at Volgograd.

The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient between the observed and modelled data for the Volga was found to be $R=0.964$. The observed annual mean monthly discharge for 1901-1935 was $8221.3 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$, and the modelled annual mean monthly discharge for the same period is $8121.7 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. The observed mean divided by the modelled mean results in a ratio of 1.01.

While the mean data for the period was found to be a good match (Figure 20), the data did not match so well on an annual basis. No correlation ($R=0.2$) was found between the yearly STREAM Volga data for 1903-1935 and the observed discharge data for the corresponding period. That there is no correlation between the two is to be expected, as the ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE run is only one of many possible iterations, so the runoff data cannot be expected to match on a temporal scale. However, the observed discharge has a much greater range than the modelled discharge. This is best demonstrated by the standard deviation, which is 1556 for the observed discharge, but only 1088 for the modelled discharge. Models are known to underestimate natural variability, so this is to be expected. Also, as was already mentioned, the ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE run used had only long term forcings. The lack of short term forcings, such as the exclusion of volcanic aerosols and sunspot cycles, could also explain the difference in standard deviation. We know that the CSL can flip from one steady state to another after sudden fluctuations in discharge, so doubts can be expressed as to whether the discharge data is sufficient for recreating CSL fluctuations, even if the long-term modelled mean is accurate.

The temporal discrepancy between the observed and modelled discharge is most likely due to the ECBilt atmospheric model. Since it is being forced by solar insolation and greenhouse gases only, it cannot accurately reproduce rainfall on a decadal scale. Also, the low resolution ($5.6^{\circ} \times 5.6^{\circ}$) means that local variations in rainfall over the catchment are not accurately modelled. However, the ECBilt atmospheric model can recreate a general rainfall regime over a wide area well, which allows STREAM to accurately model average discharge over a longer period, but not with the same inter-annual variation.

After calibrating the Volga River discharge, a comparison was made between observed and modelled discharge for the Ural River (Figure 21):

Figure 21: Modelled (1901-2000) and observed (1915-1984 [Vorosmarty et al, 1998]) Ural monthly mean discharge.

In the case of the Ural, the R value was found to be 0.966. The annual monthly observed mean is $296.8 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$, while the modelled monthly mean is $419.7 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. The observed/modelled ratio is therefore only 0.71. While the STREAM model accurately models the regime of the Ural, it overestimates the absolute value of the discharge. This could be corrected in STREAM by calibrating the evapotranspiration, through changing the crop factor (cropf) value. This would calibrate the STREAM model to the Ural River, but then the model would no longer be accurate for the Volga.

The STREAM model being employed models multiple rivers, and cannot be employed to model all of them accurately in a “one size fits all” fashion. The Volga is, as was discussed in Section 2.2, by far the most important river draining into the Caspian Sea, so the decision was made to base the calibration on the Volga. Given more time and resources, one could construct a separate STREAM model for each river draining into the Caspian Sea and calibrate each accordingly.

As such, the discharge generated by the STREAM model was separated into two entities: “Volga” and “other rivers”. The STREAM model, calibrated for the Volga, modelled the Volga properly, but systematically overestimated the other rivers. A correction factor of exactly 0.4 was applied to the discharge of the other rivers, giving the Volga an 81.9% share of the total runoff (when averaged over the entire 20th century), corresponding to the Figure of 82% given by Shiklomanov (1995). This correction factor of 0.4 was also used for other Holocene time slices, although there is no way to confirm that it will also be the correct for these periods.

4.2 Calibrating Over Sea Precipitation and Evaporation Data

When calculating the Caspian Sea water balance, the over-sea precipitation and evaporation data for the Caspian Sea will be needed. Due to the low resolution of the grid cells employed by the ECBilt atmospheric model, the Caspian Sea cell (42°N, 51°E) is seen as a “land cell.” This is far from ideal, as a body of water like the Caspian Sea has an enormous influence on the evaporation and precipitation. Additionally, a land cell does not have a high heat capacity like a water cell does, and will therefore not have the same buffered, out of season evaporation regime that a water cell has. It was decided therefore to use the precipitation and evaporation data for the eastern most Mediterranean Sea cell (36°N, 27°E) in ECBilt. This cell is located in a non-landlocked water cell at a different latitude, where the solar insolation is different. The evaporation and precipitation data for the Mediterranean would therefore have to be calibrated with the observed Caspian Sea evaporation and precipitation data for 1901-2000. This is a rather crude method of reproducing Caspian Sea P&E, and is due to the limitations of the ECBilt resolution.

The 20th century ECBilt precipitation data was corrected for mean and standard deviation according to the estimated observed 20th century values of Rodionov (1994) and Baidin and Kosarev (1986). The standard deviation of the Mediterranean ECBilt data was also corrected in order to match the standard deviation seen in the observed data. Equation 6 (Brouwer et al., 2004) was used to adjust the standard deviation and mean of the data to that of the observed values:

$$x_y = \left(\frac{x - x_{mean}}{x_{SD}} \right) \times y_{SD} + y_{mean} \quad (\text{Equation 6})$$

x_y = the corrected climate variable for a given month

x = the uncorrected climate variable for the same given month

x_{mean} = the mean of the uncorrected data for all given months

x_{SD} = the standard deviation of the uncorrected data for all given months

y_{SD} = the standard deviation of the observed data

y_{mean} = the mean of the observed data

The same approach was taken for the evaporation data, adjusting the ECBilt Mediterranean evaporation data to the 97 cm/yr estimated over-sea evaporation mean for the Caspian Sea (Rodionov 1994).

For other palaeo time periods, there is no observed Caspian Sea P&E data to compare the Mediterranean over sea precipitation and evaporation data with. For these periods the data was corrected using the same adjustment ratios as in the 20th century. For example, the 20th century ECBilt Mediterranean evaporation mean had to be corrected by a factor of 0.793 to compare with the observed 20th century evaporation mean (Rodionov, 1994) for the Caspian Sea. This same correction factor was applied to ECBilt evaporation in other palaeo time periods. There is no way of knowing whether this correction factor is also valid for these time periods. The same approach was used for correcting the evaporation's standard deviation, as well as the mean and standard deviation of the precipitation data.

Sufficiently accurate 20th observed over-sea precipitation and, particularly, evaporation data, is generally not available (Rodionov, 1994). Precipitation data is based on records from various weather station records, while evaporation data is based on estimates based on the Caspian Sea water budget. These water budget estimations for evaporation are themselves based upon the precipitation data. While the long-term mean reconstructions of evaporation and precipitation data is fairly reliable, the year-to-year variation is less reliable (Rodionov, 1994). Nevertheless, attempts have been made to reconstruct the Caspian Sea precipitation and evaporation (Rodionov 1994). Figures 23 and 24 show the available Caspian Sea precipitation and evaporation data compared to the calibrated over sea ECBilt P&E data used in this project.

Figure 22: Top: Estimated annual Caspian Sea evaporation data for the period 1890-1990 (Rodionov, 1994), with five year running mean. Bottom: ECBilt annual mean over-sea Mediterranean evaporation data for the 20th century, calibrated using mean and standard deviation of Rodionov (1994) Caspian Sea evaporation data, with five year running mean.

The calibrated ECBilt evaporation data (Figure 22) shows a similar range when compared to the Rodionov (1994) data. Departures to over 1.17 m/yr evaporation and to almost 0.77 m/yr evaporation are present in both datasets.

Figure 23: Top: Estimated annual mean Caspian Sea precipitation data for the period 1890-1990 (Rodionov, 1994), with five year running mean. Bottom: ECBilt annual mean over-sea Mediterranean precipitation data for the 20th century, calibrated for Caspian Sea using mean of Baidin and Kosarev (1986) and standard deviation of Rodionov (1994), with five year running mean.

The corrected precipitation data (Figure 23) shows a similar range to the Rodionov data for the 1900-1960 period. The shift to higher values between 1960 and 1980 is not present in the corrected data however. The climate model used uses long-term forcings only, meaning that inter-decadal shifts found in the observed data cannot be expected to be realistically modelled. Also, the fact the Mediterranean ECBilt data is being recalibrated as Caspian Sea data could also be an explanation as to why the trends in precipitation do not match. Different climate processes could be at work in these different regions. However, the shift in the observed data from 1960 onwards may also be due to natural variability. The ECBilt model run is just one of many possible random outcomes and one cannot expect the data to match exactly on a temporal scale, even if the model had correctly resolved the Caspian Sea and recalibrated Mediterranean data didn't have to be used.

5.0 Selection and Preparation of Model Runs

Before running the model, the decision must be taken as to which time periods will be analysed. Seeing as the ECBilt-Clio-Vecode model used as climate input for STREAM is driven only by the long-term variables of solar insolation and greenhouse forcing, it was decided that time slices taking this into account would be used. Any palaeoclimatic periods analysed would have to be significantly long enough in order to examine processes beyond the decadal timescale. As such, it was decided that 400 year periods would be used for the palaeo-runs.

When calculating the CSL curve, the ECBilt over sea precipitation and evaporation data for the corresponding period were used, calibrated as detailed in Section 4.2.

5.1 20th Century Model Run

The STREAM model was run for the 20th century, with the calibration factors as detailed in the calibration section (4.1) of this paper. The purpose of the 20th century model run is to see how the results compare with observed CSL values. The Caspian Sea water balance equation was run with STREAM discharge output and with corrected P & E data from the Mediterranean Sea (as detailed in Section 4.2). The starting value for the CSL run was set at -26 metres elevation, corresponding to the observed value for 1901.

5.2 6200-5801 BP Model Run

One of the first ideas was to examine what effect the mid-Holocene period (circa 6000 BP), also known as the Holocene climatic optimum, would have on the Volga and the CSL. During this period, orbital parameters caused increased warming in the northern hemisphere, especially during the summer. According to a coupled atmosphere-ocean-vegetation model (Ganopolski et al., 1998) based on 6000 BP orbital parameters, the extra-tropical northern hemisphere landmass temperatures were some 2.5° C higher in summer and 0.4° C higher in winter, when compared to pre-industrial values. The increased warming was partly due to positive feedbacks due to albedo changes caused by increased vegetation and decreased sea-ice cover (some 27% reduction). A rise in precipitation, when compared to pre-industrial values, for northern hemisphere land areas was also modelled, and found to be increased by 0.54 mm/day in summer and 0.05 mm/day in winter. In turn, increased runoff from continents was also modelled, causing bodies of water associated with deep water formation to freshen, thus weakening the thermohaline circulation. Ganopolski et al. (1998) used the CLIMBER model to recreate shifts in vegetation and claim that the modelled shifts correspond to the pollen proxies of Prentice et al. (1996). According to pollen reconstructions of Prentice et al. (1996), the summer temperatures in Europe were some 2° C higher than today. This compares well with the 2.5° C

northern hemisphere landmass temperature modelled by Ganopolski et al. (1998).

ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE also simulates 6200-5800 BP average temperature as being warmer than pre-industrial values. Renssen et al. (2005) found that temperatures north of 60° N have cooled steadily from 9000 BP to pre-industrial times, by some 2° Celsius in total. This also agrees with the orbital calculations of Berger and Loutre (2002), which show insolation at 65° N as decreasing over the past 10,000 years.

6200-5800 BP, as modelled by ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE, is found however to have cooler temperatures than the 20th century (see Appendix B2). This can be attributed to higher CO₂ greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere in the 20th century. 6200-5800 BP precipitation was modelled by ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE as markedly higher than the 20th century, especially over the Volga catchment (see Appendix C2). It would be interesting to see how the Caspian Sea responds to this higher precipitation. More precipitation would cause increased Volga discharge causing the CSL to rise, and the lower temperatures associated with the 6200-5800 BP period (when compared to the 20th century) would also cause less evaporation over the Caspian Sea, also contributing to a CSL rise. It should therefore be expected that CSL simulated for the 6200-5800 BP period will be higher than that simulated in the 20th century.

The 6200-5801 BP period was run with the same STREAM model that was used to calibrate the Volga river output in the 20th century calibration run. The 1992 AD crop factor map (cropf) was replaced by the corresponding cropf map for the 6200-5801 BP period (De Moel, 2005; Ward, 2005), and the precipitation and temperature data was replaced with the corresponding data for the 6200-5801 BP period.

In order to calculate the CSL curve, a starting value for the CSL had to be prescribed. It was found that the CSL sought an elevation of -21.8 m at the end of the 6200-5801 BP run, no matter what value (in the range of -20 m to -30 m) was entered as a start value. It was therefore decided that -21.8 m would be used as the starting value for the 6200-5801 BP CSL curve.

5.3 3400-3001 BP Model Run

The 3400-3001 BP period can be said to be between the pre-industrial and 6200-5801 BP periods in terms of overall temperature (H. Renssen, personal communication). In other words, warmer than pre-industrial values, but cooler than the 6200-5801 BP Holocene optimum period. ECBilt simulates the temperature of the 3400-3001 BP period as cooler than both the 6200-5801 BP period and the 20th century (see Appendix B2). Precipitation over the catchment area is simulated as less than 6200-5801 BP, but more than the 20th century (see Appendix C2).

The STREAM model was run with the relevant cropf (De Moel, 2005; Ward, 2005) and climate input data for the 3400-3000 BP period. In order to calculate the CSL curve, a starting value for the CSL had to be prescribed. It was found that the CSL sought an elevation of -22.6 m at the end of the 3400-3001 BP run, no matter what value (in the range of -20 m to -30 m) was entered as a start value. It was therefore decided that -22.6 m would be used as the starting value for the 6200-5801 BP CSL curve.

Figure 24: Calibrated over sea P-E (nine year smooth), modelled STREAM Volga discharge (nine year smooth) and modelled CSL (annual).

6.0 Results & Discussion

6.1 20th Century

The CSL for this period clearly fluctuates in a two metre elevation range between -25 metres and -27 metres (see Figure 24). Between 1910 and 1950 an overall increasing trend is noted in the CSL. This corresponds with an overall modelled increasing trend in both P-E and Volga discharge. The following correlations were found between the various variables and the yearly CSL flux (Table 3):

Variable	Correlation with annual Δ CSL
Annual Volga discharge	R=0.71
Annual discharge for all rivers	R=0.82
Annual over sea P-E	R=0.61

Table 3: 1901-2000 AD correlation between annual Δ CSL and various factors.

Both over sea P-E and river discharge together contribute to the changes in CSL. However, from the correlations it would seem that changes in river discharge have a greater influence over the sea level flux than changes in over sea P-E, seeing as the correlation is much higher for the former. However, it would agree with the findings of Arkhipova et al. (1970) who found that changes in 20th century CSL were more to do with changes in river runoff than over sea P-E (70% due to runoff, 28% due to P-E). The correlation of 0.82 found between river discharge and Δ CSL exactly matches the value reported by Arpe et al. (2000).

Observed CSL in the 20th century varied between -25.9 m and -29.1 m, an amplitude of 3.2 m. However, according to Rodionov (1994), this extreme change in CSL was compounded by the anthropogenic changes brought on by damming schemes on the rivers leading to the Caspian Sea. His non-anthropogenic reconstruction (Fig. 8) suggests that the Caspian Sea would have fluctuated between -25.6 m and -28 m (amplitude of 2.4 m) if the rivers had been left undisturbed. The CSL model in this paper shows a fluctuation between -25.0 m and -27.0 m, an amplitude of 2 m, comparable to the amplitude of Rodionov (1994) [Fig. 8]. Elguindi and Giorgi's (2006) ensemble average for their 20th century CSL model runs was between -26 m and -27.6 m, so one could conclude that the CSL modelled by the ECBilt-STREAM-CSL approach has an accuracy approaching that of Elguindi and Giorgi's approach. It would be interesting to see how the results the couple STREAM-CSL approach would compare with those of Elguindi and Giorgi if the same climate model input data was used.

The mean sea level is -25.9 m, one metre higher than the mean of -26.9 m according to Rodionov's non-anthropogenic reconstruction. This could be due to the fact that although the Volga has been calibrated over a 35 year period, other rivers draining into the Caspian Sea covered in the STREAM

model were calibrated less accurately, due to a lack of discharge data. Secondly, the aforementioned 35 year period used to calibrate the Volga may not be a sufficiently long enough period.

The main conclusion that we can take from these results is that the offline coupled ECBilt-STREAM-CSL model shows decadal shifts in CSL despite ECBilt using long-term forcings. In the ECBilt-STREAM-CSL model we see shifts of almost a metre within a decade and two metre shifts over a fifty year period. The goal of the modelling exercise was to have a model that simulated long term trends in CSL, as well as short term excursions. The long term regime is that of a CSL similar to the observed value, and short term excursions have also been successfully simulated.

Figure 25: Calibrated over sea P-E (nine year smooth), modelled STREAM Volga discharge (nine year smooth) and modelled CSL (yearly).

6.2 6200-5801 BP

The CSL during the 6200-5801 BP period, as simulated by the ECBilt-STREAM-CSL model (Figure 25), is higher than the 20th century. This is what was expected, due to the increased precipitation over the Volga catchment (see Appendix C2), leading to a 4.3% increase in river discharge when compared to the 20th century (see Table 4). An increase in discharge for this period is also found by Aerts et al. (2006), who simulated that 6200-5800 BP discharge was some 7% higher when compared to 1750-2000 AD, agreeing with the proxy analysis of Ward (in press).

According to Rychagov (1997, see Figure 10) the 6200-5800 BP period was marked by a highstand of -21 m, preceded by a significant lowstand. The highstand is reproduced well by the model, although there is no modelled lowstand. The simulated ECBilt-STREAM-CSL sea level does not show an overall trend, but rather a fluctuation between -19.4 m and -22.6 m. It is possible that the lowstand is not simulated by ECBilt due to the absence of short term forcings, such as volcanic activity and sunspot cycles. It is also possible that Rychagov overestimates the intensity of the lowstands. In any case, in order to discern if a longer term trend is present, the model should be run for a longer time period.

Large decadal scale fluctuations in CSL are found, which suggest that fluctuations in CSL were also present before times of large anthropogenic influence. Most illustrative is the sea level drop of 1.66 m between 6044 and 6029 BP (see Figure 25), where low discharge coincides with a major reduction in P-E. Between 6156 and 6132 BP we see a temporary drop in CSL due to a drop in river discharge. Once the river discharge is restored to a higher level, the CSL level recovers to near the 6156 BP level.

Variable	Correlation with annual ΔCSL
Annual Volga discharge	R=0.64
Annual discharge for all rivers	R=0.71
Annual over sea P-E	R=0.61

Table 4: 6200-5801 BP correlation between annual Δ CSL and various factors.

Correlation between Volga discharge, as well as all rivers, and Δ CSL was found to be lower than in the 20th century. This could be due to the longer model run (400 years). Correlation between (P-E) and Δ CSL was found to be the same.

Figure 26: Calibrated ECBilt over sea P-E (nine year smooth), modelled STREAM Volga discharge (nine year smooth) and modelled CSL (yearly).

Period	Averaged River Discharge		Over-Sea Data			CSL Average (m)
	Volga Q (km ³ /yr)	All Rivers Q (km ³ /yr)	P (cm/yr)	E (cm/yr)	P-E (cm/yr)	
1901-2000 AD	260.1	318.0	18.0	97.0	-79.0	-25.9
3400-3000 BP	259.8	329.1	19.7	96.9	-77.2	-23.6
6200-5800 BP	271.2	344.5	20.5	97.5	-77.0	-21.2

Table 5: Average simulated river discharges, average corrected over-sea data and simulated CSL for the 20th century, 6200-5801 BP and 3400-3000 BP.

6.3 3400-3001 BP

The simulated CSL for the 3400-3001 BP time period is found to be in between that of 6200-5801 BP and the 20th century (see Table 5), which would agree with the fact that ECBilt simulates 3400-3001 BP precipitation as less than 5800-6201 BP, but more than the 20th century (see Appendix C2). Over-sea P-E is found to be very similar to 6200-5801 BP, and Volga discharge is modelled as almost exactly the same as for the 20th century. Extra discharge in this period, when compared to the 20th century, is attributed to other rivers besides the Volga.

Once again, just as in the other time periods, sharp decadal shifts in CSL are noted (see Figure 26). A shift of 1.74 m is noted in a period of only seven years, between 3124 and 3117 BP, this due to a sudden rise in both river discharge and over-sea P-E. A similar drop in CSL is noted between 3042 and 3037 BP, caused by a sharp reduction in river discharge combined with lower than average P-E.

According to Rychagov (1997, see Figure 10) the 3400-3001 BP period featured a CSL which fluctuated sharply with -23 m as a highstand. The CSL simulated during this research fluctuates mostly below -23 m, although it fluctuates above -23 m slightly at some points, reaching as high as -22.5. This would seem to agree with Rychagov's palaeogeographic reconstruction, but a longer run, with better input data, is needed in order to confirm this.

Variable	Correlation with annual Δ CSL
Annual Volga discharge	R=0.61
Annual discharge for all rivers	R=0.71
Annual over sea P-E	R=0.50

Table 6: 3400-3000 BP correlation between annual Δ CSL and various factors.

The correlation between P-E and Δ CSL was found to be much lower during the 3400-3001 BP period than the other two time slices modelled.

6.4 Discussion of all Time slices

The modelled long-term CSL for the different time periods was found to broadly agree with the palaeogeographic reconstructions as well as observed data (see Table 7). The long term trend in CSL is found to be mostly due to changes in river discharge and over sea precipitation.

	<i>ECBilt STREAM CSL Average</i>	<i>ECBilt STREAM CSL Range</i>	<i>Rychagov Palaeo- geograph Range</i>			
6200 – 5801 BP	-21.2	-19.4 to -22.6 (3.2 m)	-21 to ?	<i>Observed CSL range</i>	<i>Rodionov non- anthropogenic reconstruction</i>	<i>Giorgi and Elguindi ensemble range</i>
3400 – 3001 BP	-23.6	-22.5 to -24.7 (2.2 m)	-23 to ?			
20th century	-25.9	-25.0 to -27 (2.0 m)	-25 to -29 (4 m)	-25.9 to -29.1 (3.2 m)	-25.6 to -28.0 (2.4 m)	-26 to -27.6 (1.6 m)

Table 7: Comparison of Caspian Sea Level studies. (ECBilt-STREAM-CSL [This study]; Rychagov, 1997; , Rodionov, 1994; Giorgi and Elguindi, 2006)

While the average CSL is modelled quite well, the overall trends found in Rychagov’s palaeogeographic reconstructions are not found. ECBilt-VECODE-CLIO is a model based on long-term climate forcings, and as such a much longer model run is needed in order to see any long term changes in CSL which could then be compared to Rychagov’s reconstructions.

Annual over-sea evaporation is found, in this study, to change very little (see Table 5). This is could of course be due to the fact that the corrected Mediterranean data is being used, as opposed to evaporation data modelled for the Caspian Sea. However, while the average evaporation data may be the same annually, the changes in CSL may also be affected by evaporation changes on a seasonal level. According to Kutzbach and Street-Perrot (1985), the orbital parameters of the Earth caused more extreme seasonal differences in solar insolation in the Northern hemisphere during the mid Holocene (see Figure 27).

Figure 27: Kutzbach and Street-Perrot's (1985) Holocene climate forcings reconstruction.

Increased summer insolation would have led to higher evaporation during the summer, but with winter insolation being reduced by a similar amount, leading to less evaporation. As such, while the annual over-sea evaporation for the 20th century and the 6200-5800 BP period may have been the same annually, great seasonal differences can be expected. This Northern Hemisphere phenomenon is confirmed in the uncorrected monthly Mediterranean evaporation as modelled by ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE, which shows decreasing seasonality for time slices closer to the present day (see Figure 28).

Figure 28: Uncorrected monthly Mediterranean Evaporation data for three time slices, as simulated by ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE.

In the case of increased seasonality over the the Caspian Sea, over-sea evaporation in summer would be accompanied by reduced over-sea evaporation during winter. As such, it could be suggested that intra-annual variation in CSL was much greater during the mid-Holocene than now. Less insolation during mid-Holocene winters would also cause harsher winters and lead to an increase in the winter strength of positive NAO phases, leading to more snow accumulation over the Caspian basin. This could explain why ECBilt simulates more precipitation over the Volga catchment for 6200-5801 BP than the 3400-3001 BP period, with the 20th century showing less precipitation than both periods.

With global warming we can expect the temperature to rise at an annual level, e.g. warmer winters as well as warmer summers. Warmer summers will lead to a greater and longer evaporation season, while winters will also warm, leading to increases evaporation in that time of the year too. Unlike in the mid-Holocene, where there was less insolation during winter, which compensated increased summer insolation, we could see an overall annual increase in over-sea evaporation in the 21st century. Elguindi and Giorgi (2006) predict a large increase in annual over-sea evaporation, causing a fall in CSL to -35 metres elevation by 2100.

6.5 Critical Discussion

There are a number of weak points in this study that need to be addressed. The first major weak point is the fact that a single STREAM model is used for modelling the entire Caspian basin. Ideally, a separate STREAM model calibrated for each major river would be used. Each river would be both calibrated and validated based on hydrological records spanning a suitable time period.

Another weakness in this study is the fact that a single precipitation and evaporation value is used for the entire Caspian Sea. Seeing that the sea spans such a large area from north to south, with differing solar insolation, we can expect different evaporation for the southern and northern parts of the sea. The influence of winter ice formation in the north of the sea was also not taken into account.

A minor weak point in this study is the use of a constant value (2.7 cm/yr) for loss due to discharge into the Bay of Kara-Bogaz-Gol. As the sea level rises and falls, overspill into the Bay will increase and decrease. If the sea level decreases enough, overspill into the Bay could be cut off altogether. However, changes in this overspill play a very small role in the yearly sea level change. Elguindi and Giorgi (2006) also use a constant value to represent this factor.

The fact that the Caspian Sea is seen as a land cell by the resolution of the ECBilt model is the most glaring weak point in this study. This influences both the temperature and precipitation modelled around the Caspian Sea area, which has consequences for the catchments modelled in STREAM. There was no available ECBilt over-sea precipitation and evaporation data for the Caspian Sea, and adjusted data from the Mediterranean Sea had to be used instead. Using a model that resolves the Caspian Sea would of course have been preferential, but the method used proved to be a good alternative when modelling long term trends.

Even with these weaknesses, it is surprising that the CSL modelled for the three time slices studied had results broadly similar to those of Rychagov's palaeogeographic reconstructions. In this respect, this study shows that the coupled ECBilt-STREAM-CSL approach can work for simulating the Caspian Sea level long term, although not yet accurately enough so that the results can be trusted to a satisfactory level. With this in mind, it would be interesting to see how the ECBilt-STREAM-CSL approach to the Caspian Sea would fare with increased spatial resolution in the ECBilt module, with both precipitation and evaporation of the Caspian Sea accurately modelled. As computers continue to advance in power, it will be possible to increase the resolution of the climate model in the future.

7.0 Conclusion

In this study a coupled ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE model was successfully coupled offline with STREAM to produce an acceptably accurate model for the Volga catchment. A sea level model, coupled offline to both STREAM and ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE, was also constructed, which takes the morphology of the sea basin into account allowing the dynamics of fluctuating sea level and sea area to be simulated. It has been shown that, with these relatively basic tools, the long term CSL trend can be modelled using the methodology outlined in this paper. A long term decreasing CSL trend since the Holocene optimum is noted, namely an average of -21.2 m for the 6200-5800 BP period, -23.6 m for 3400-3000 BP and -25.9 m for the 20th century. This is consistent with available estimates based on palaeogeographic reconstructions (Rychagov, 1997). A much longer run, possibly for the entire Holocene epoch, is needed to confirm this trend, however.

Sharp, decadal changes in the order of 1.5 m were also noted in the simulated CSL for all time slices. This is especially noteworthy when it is considered that the climate model employed only uses long term, non-decadal climate forcing, which would suggest that decadal CSL changes can be caused by internal climate variability alone. This suggests that sudden, decadal scale sea level shifts are a typical, inherent behaviour for the endorheic Caspian Sea. This is not to say however that changes in CSL are down to natural variability alone. Human influence, in the form of river engineering and climate change, can cause the long term changes in the sea's water budget, causing the overall, absolute value of the CSL to change considerably. Past Holocene changes in the water budget, in the form of changing watershed precipitation and over-sea evaporation, occurred due to climate sensitivity. As we are entering, or have perhaps already entered, a period of significant anthropogenic climate change, the Caspian Sea's water budget will once again undergo marked changes.

With improved input data, particularly for over sea precipitation and evaporation, as well as improved calibration and validation of the various other catchments of the Caspian Basin, the model could be refined to a satisfactory level.

8.0 Future Research

There is much scope with which to take this research project further. The STEAM-CSL coupled model could be run for the 20th century using the CRU dataset instead of ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE. The simulated 20th century CSL could then be compared to the observed CSL, as a way to validate the STREAM-CSL coupled model. Great care must be taken that STREAM discharge is correctly calibrated, as the hydrological regimes of the Volga River before and after the implementation of hydro-electric schemes in the early 20th century are essentially those of two completely different rivers.

When the STREAM-CSL coupled model is properly validated in this way, it can be considered a more trusted hydrological-sea level model which can then be run based on the datasets from other climate models, including IPCC scenario models for the 21st century, or various other palaeoclimate models, including ECBilt.

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Appendix A

Stream Script

```
#Reading initial values
Import(APWL, 'input\init\')
Import(GW, 'input\init\')
Import(SNOW, 'input\init\')
Import(SOILSTOR, 'input\init\')
Import(MASK, 'input\etc\')
Import(MMTOQ, 'input\etc\')

#Reading Thorntwaite parameters
Import(H, 'input\etc\')
Import(A, 'input\etc\')
Import(WATERH, 'input\etc\')
Import(C, 'input\etc\')
Import(BPGLDD, 'input\etc\')
Import(CROPF, 'input\etc\')

WHOLDN = WATERH * 1.0
HEAT = H * 1.0

#Reading climate scenario data...
ImportTimer(TMP, %ClimateChange)
ImportTimer(PRE, %ClimateChange)
TMP = (TMP/10)
PRE = (PRE/10)

#SNOW***SNOW***SNOW
#Calculating snow fall, snow cover storage and snow melt...
SNOW1 = mif(TMP < 0, PRE, 0)
SNOW = SNOW + SNOW1
MELT = mif(TMP > 0, 9 * TMP, 0)
SNOW2 = min(SNOW, MELT)
SNOW = SNOW - SNOW2
PRE = PRE + SNOW2 - SNOW1

#Calculate potential evapotranspiration using Thornthwaite,
EVEN1 = TMP / HEAT
EVEN2 = mif(EVEN1 > 100, 1, EVEN1)
EVEN3 = mif(EVEN2 < -100, 1, EVEN2)
PE = 16 * ((10 * EVEN1)^A)
PE = mif(PE > 500, 500, PE)
EVEN = -415.85 + 32.24 * TMP - 0.43 * TMP^2
PE = mif(TMP > 26.5, EVEN, PE)
PE = mif(TMP <= 0, 0, PE)
PE = PE * CROPF * 0.66

#Calculate soil storage according to Thornthwaite-Mather ...
PEFF = PRE - PE
APWL = mif(PEFF < 0, APWL - PEFF, 0)
EVEN = SOILSTOR + PRE - PE
SSTOR = mif(PEFF > 0, EVEN, WHOLDN * exp(-APWL / WHOLDN))
AE = mif(PEFF >= 0, PE, PRE + SOILSTOR - SSTOR)
TOGW = mif(PEFF >= 0, max(0, SOILSTOR + PEFF - WHOLDN), 0)
SOILSTOR = max(0.01, SOILSTOR + PRE - AE - TOGW)
APWL = mif(SOILSTOR < WHOLDN, WHOLDN * ln(WHOLDN+1 /
SOILSTOR), 0)

#Separate direct from delayed runoff (seepage to groundwater)...
RUNOFF = 0.4 * TOGW
TOGW = TOGW - RUNOFF

#Calculate volume of groundwater and baseflow...
GW = GW + TOGW
```

```

SLOFLO      = GW / (C * 7)
GW          = GW - SLOFLO

#Calculate discharge (snow melt + runoff + baseflow),
#and create map of total monthly discharge per cel...

DSCHRG      = RUNOFF + SLOFLO

#ExportTimer(DSCHRG, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\Dis.pal')
#ExportTimer(MELT2, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\Dis.pal')
#ExportTimer(RUNOFF, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\Dis.pal')
#ExportTimer(SLOFLO, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\Dis.pal')

#Recalculate mm -> m^3; accumulate discharge and calculate m^3/sec
DSCHRG      = DSCHRG * MMTOQ
DISQ        = accu(BPGLDD, DSCHRG, 'input\')
timeout(DISQ, %DischargePoints, %OutputDirectory)

#Accumulate discharge from above lying cels (in mm and in m3/sec),
#and create discharge graphs...
DISMM       = accu(BPGLDD, DSCHRG, 'Input\')
timeout(DISMM, %DischargePoints, %OutputDirectory)
#ExportTimer(DISMM, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\Dis.pal')
#ExportTimer(DSCHRG, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\Dis.pal')

DISQSEC     = DISMM * ((55567*22640)*0.001) / 2592000
ExportTimer(DISQSEC, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\Dis.pal')
timeout(DISQSEC, %DischargePoints, %OutputDirectory)

#ExportTimer(SNOW, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\snow.pal')
#ExportTimer(TMP, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\temp.pal')
#ExportTimer(PRE, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\prec.pal')
#ExportTimer(PE, %OutputDirectory, 'Input\Palettes\prec.pal')

#Export init-maps
Export(APWL, %OutputDirectory)
Export(GW, %OutputDirectory)
Export(SNOW, %OutputDirectory)
Export(SOILSTOR, %OutputDirectory)

#Summarize (give max, min and average) for Actual evapotranspiration,
#Potential evapotranspiration, groundwater budget and snow cover...

#TSummary(AE, %OutputDirectory)
TSummary(PE, %OutputDirectory)
#TSummary(GW, %OutputDirectory)
TSummary(SNOW, %OutputDirectory)
TSummary(TMP, %OutputDirectory)
TSummary(PRE, %OutputDirectory)

#...End of iteration.

```

Appendix B1

Average ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE temperature data per time slice, downscaled by De Moel (2005).

Appendix B2

ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE temperature differences

6200-5800 BP average temperature minus 3400-3000 BP average temperature.
Green cells indicate 6200-5800 BP warmer.
Yellow, purple and black cells indicate 3400-3000 BP warmer.

6200-5800 BP average temperature minus 1901-2000 AD average temperature.

Appendix B2 (continued)

ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE temperature differences (continued)

3400-3000 BP average temperature minus 1901-2000 AD average temperature.

Appendix C1

Average ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE precipitation data per time slice, downscaled by De Moel (2005).

Appendix C2

ECBilt-CLIO-VECODE precipitation differences

Appendix D

Flow map:

Example of a corresponding discharge map (with masked basin):

